

Exploring Advanced Deep Learning Models for Super Resolution of 3D Dental CBCT Volumes

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Abstract. High Resolution plays an important role in digital imaging, but it is even more important in medical imaging. However, due to certain constraints, medical imaging is often captured in low dose radiation which causes noise and lower resolution. As high resolution plays a vital role in diagnostics and model training, we compare efficiency and accuracy of state-of-the-art deep learning models for super-resolution reconstruction in 3D volumes. We have employed various deep learning models, such as CNN, SR-GAN, UNet and Auto-Encoder for super resolution-reconstruction of 3D Dental CBCT volumes. To optimize their performance, we have combined different architectural enhancements such as multipath structure in CNN and SR-GAN for enhanced features extraction, Mamba with UNet to capture global dependencies, and Diffusion with Auto-Encoder for feature refinement. The performance of CNN is highest with Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio and Structural Similarity Index of 35.35 and 0.952 respectively; however, Auto-Encoder is the fastest with training time of 28.63 hours.

Keywords: 3D imaging, Volumes, CBCT, super resolution, deep learning.

1 Introduction

High Resolution (HR) images provide greater detail than low-resolution (LR) images and are often preferred in various medical imaging applications. However, capturing images in HR is challenging due to expensive imaging devices, long acquisition times, high storage and bandwidth [1]. Additionally, HR medical images often require prolonged exposure to high radiation, which can be harmful and cause discomfort [2]. Super Resolution (SR) techniques are an effective alternative solution to reconstruct HR images from LR inputs which reduces the mentioned complications. SR aims to recover lost fine details from LR images but is a challenging task due to variations in anatomical structures, modalities and types of images. It seeks to reconstruct images with fine details from LR images, a task particularly vital in medical imaging where even minor artefacts can compromise diagnostic accuracy by affecting critical features like tumor boundaries in MRI or subtle vascular changes in retinal images [3, 4].

Super resolution methods are categorized into classical machine learning and deep learning methods. Classical approaches such as interpolation-based methods often blur fine anatomical details [4,5], while classical machine learning method such as random

forest offer limited accuracy [6]. Recently, deep learning models such as CNNs, UNets, GANs and Transformers have shown superior performance, especially in medical imaging [4]. Cone Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT), widely used in oral healthcare due to its low radiation and 3D capability however, suffers from noise and low resolution that compromises diagnosis [9]. While various deep learning models have been explored for 3D medical imaging SR, literature remains limited for CBCT [10, 11]. Several studies have explored SR reconstruction using dental CBCT data, such as authors in [7] have used CBCT data of teeth for super resolution; various deep learning models are evaluated for SR on 32 CBCT volumes in [8]; Kazimierczak et al [9] propose a Vendor-Agnostic based noise reduction and super resolution model. However, challenges like use of synthetic datasets, generalization issues, artefact introduction, complexity of models, and low accuracy persist. To address these gaps, this paper explores a range of models and multiple architectures to propose an advanced deep learning framework based on a real clinical dataset for dental CBCT SR.

Figure 1: Sagittal view of 3D CBCT volume, comparing low resolution (left) and high resolution

2 Methodology

2.1 System Model

The research methodology is illustrated in Figure 2. The workflow begins with the left-most node, which represents the dataset used for conducting the experiments. During the pre-processing stage, high-resolution 3D volumes serve as the ground truth, while corresponding low-resolution volumes are generated from these HR volumes to serve as input to the deep learning network. Due to the high memory requirements of 3D volumes, memory optimization techniques are necessary to enable training on resource-constrained machines. To address this, we employ a random patch selection method [10].

The deep learning network comprises three main components: feature extraction, image generation, and loss calculation. While a general deep learning architecture is illustrated in Figure 2, multiple models have been implemented in our experiments, including CNN, SRGAN, Mamba U-Net, and a diffusion-based Auto-Encoder [13]. For baseline comparison, the Dilated Convolutional Super-Resolution Network (DCSRN) model is also utilized.

The loss function acts as a weight adjustment mechanism, comparing each LR patch with its corresponding ground truth patch and guiding the model in updating weights for the next epoch. As the model iteratively trains, it gradually converges into a usable state. In addition to the loss function, evaluation metrics such as PSNR and SSIM are employed to assess model performance during both training and testing phases.

Figure 2: Overview of the methodology, illustrating data collection, pre-processing, model training, testing, and evaluation

2.2 Dataset

The dataset we have used was obtained from Figshare [12], an online digital repository that enables researchers to store, share, and manage data in a variety of formats. The dataset comprises 200 3D dental Cone-Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) volumes, each with a resolution of approximately $600 \times 600 \times 500$ voxels. During pre-processing, the LR volumes were obtained using trilinear interpolation and HR are kept as ground truth. For memory optimization, patches of size $64 \times 64 \times 64$ were extracted from both the LR and HR.

3 Results and Discussion

As discussed earlier, we present a cross-family comparison of deep learning models for super-resolution reconstruction in 3D volumetric data. For this case study, we utilize 3D dental CBCT volumes and evaluate four representative models from different architectural families: Multi-Path 3D CNN, Multi-Path 3D SRGAN, Mamba UNet, and Auto-Encoder with Diffusion. For benchmarking purposes, we also compare these models against a widely recognized baseline for super-resolution, DCSRN.

All models are trained and tested under the same environment (The super-resolution experiments were conducted in PyTorch 2.2.0 on an NVIDIA RTX A4000 (16 GB VRAM) using Python 3.10 and CUDA 12.8. Training used the Adam optimizer ($\text{lr}=2e-4$), L1 loss, patch size of 64^3 , and batch size of 1 due to memory constraints.), using identical hyper parameters and dataset sizes. As shown in Figure 3, the models are evaluated based on PSNR, SSIM, total execution time (training + evaluation) and No. of Parameters (which play crucial role in determining the model’s complexity, learning capacity and computational cost). The Multi-Path 3D CNN achieves the highest PSNR and SSIM scores, outperforming all other models, including DCSRN, but requires long processing time. DCSRN ranks second in terms of PSNR and SSIM, yet

its computational time remains comparable to that of CNN. The Mamba UNet ranks third in terms of image quality metrics. The Multi-Path 3D SRGAN achieves a PSNR of 39.97 and an SSIM of 93.5%, which are relatively lower than other models; however, it offers improved time performance. Among all evaluated models, the Auto-Encoder with Diffusion ranks lowest in PSNR and SSIM, yet it demonstrates efficiency in terms of training time.

Figure 3: This chart demonstrates the performance of Models in terms of PSNR, SSIM, Execution Time and No. of Parameters, normalized relative to CNN Generator. Real values for CNN Generator are shown for reference. (Note: Bar for #Parameters for Mamba-UNet and AE-Diffusion have been truncated for clarity; actual values shown above the bar.)

We have also conducted an ablation study with different dataset size such as 200, 150 and 100 volumes, but except a change in execution time, no significant differences were noted in terms of No. of parameters, PSNR and SSIM.

4 Conclusion

In this paper, we proposed and evaluated super resolution models using deep learning for enhancing 3D dental CBCT images on 200 clinical volumes. Our comparative analysis of the models mentioned demonstrates an effective way forward in improving image quality without incurring huge training costs. This work offers a practical foundation for SR in dental to improve diagnostics accuracy while using LR images which avoid harmful radiation exposure. Going forward, we aim to test the models on data from diverse sources and continue exploring other models. Additionally, we aim to explore other SOTA architectures that are relevant for resource constrained environments often encountered in practical situations.

5 Data Availability

The dataset used in this study is publicly available¹ while source code is accessible on github². All plots and visualizations are shared via OSF under project “3D-CBCT-Super-Resolution”.

¹ https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/_b_3D_multimodal_dental_dataset_based_on_CBCT_and_oral_scan_b_/26965903

² <https://github.com/2802990u/3D-CBCT-Super-Resolution->

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